

STABILITY INDICATING ANALYTICAL METHOD AND VALIDATION OF A UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF LEVOSULPIRIDE IN BULK AND ITS FORMULATION

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ABSTRACT

A simple, sensitive, and selective UV spectrophotometric method was successfully developed and validated for the estimation of Levosulpiride. The method utilized UV spectrometry, with the maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) observed at 291 nm. The optimized concentration was determined to be 80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, corresponding to an absorbance of 0.517. The assay method demonstrated excellent validation parameters, with a linearity coefficient of 0.9981. Precision and accuracy showed a %RSD of less than 2, while recovery studies yielded results within the range of 98-102% (%RSD). Various stability studies, including LOQ, LOD, and robustness, confirmed the method's reliability, with LOD and LOQ values below 10. Robustness testing showed % assay results ranging from 98-102%. Stability studies indicated the method remained stable under different conditions, and degradation studies under acidic and basic environments revealed less than 10% degradation, with % assay values maintained between 98-102%. The method was also effectively applied to the routine analysis of Levosulpiride using UV spectrophotometry, where LOD and LOQ values were determined to be 0.9726 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 2.9531 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Keywords: Method Development UV -Visible spectroscopy, levosulpiride, Degradation studies

INTRODUCTION:

Levosulpiride is primarily used for gastrointestinal disorders like treating GERD, dyspepsia, and IBS by enhancing gastric motility. And also used as an atypical antipsychotic and antidepressant for mild schizophrenia and depression due to its selective dopamine D2 antagonist activity. Helps in delayed gastric emptying and nausea¹.

The IUPAC name of Levosulpiride is:

(S)- (-)-5-(Amino sulfonyl)-N-[(1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-yl) methyl]-2-methoxybenzamide

Figure 1: chemical structure of levosulpiride

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The Shimadzu UV-1800 is a UV-Visible Double Beam Spectrophotometer equipped with UV-Probe software, manufactured in Japan. The Soltech 2200MH Ultrasonicator, manufactured by Spincotech Pvt. Ltd. The NO-HT220 Electric Digital Balance, manufactured by Vibro Shinko Denshi Co. Ltd., are a highly precise and reliable instruments designed for accurate measurements in laboratory and industrial applications². Pharmaceutical grade levosulpiride was supplied by Yarrow Chem Products Private Ltd., Mumbai, India. And Analytical-grade methanol was used from SD Fine-Chem Limited, Mumbai, India.

METHODOLOGY:

- **Selection of solvent:**
The solubility test for levosulpiride was conducted using various solvents, including ethanol, 0.1N NaOH, and 0.1N HCl, as reported in the literature. Additionally, methanol, water, and 50% methanol were also tested. Among these, 50% methanol was selected as the optimal solvent for method development³.
- **Preparation of standard stock solution**
In a 10 mL volumetric flask, 10 mg of levosulpiride API was accurately weighed and dissolved in 10 mL of 50% methanol. The solution was then made up to the mark, resulting in a final concentration of 1000 µg/mL.
- **Preparation of working standard solution**
A 0.8mL aliquot of the stock solution was taken and diluted to 10 mL with distilled water, resulting in a final concentration of 80 µg/mL
- **Preparation of sample solution**
An accurately weighed amount of powdered tablet equivalent to 25 mg of levosulpiride was quantitatively transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask. The drug was dissolved in 50% methanol and the volume was adjusted accordingly. The solution was then sonicated for 15 minutes to ensure complete dissolution. From this stock solution, an appropriate volume was further diluted with distilled water to obtain a final concentration of 80 µg/mL⁴.
- **Determination of λ_{max}**
Aliquots of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1 and 1.25mL from the working standard solution were pipetted into 10 mL volumetric flasks, and the volume was made up to the mark with distilled water to achieve concentrations of 20, 40, 60, 80 and 120 µg/mL. The 80µl of stock solution was diluted to 10 ml with water (8µg/ml). The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured against the respective blank solution (50%v/v Methanol) in the UV region of 200-400nm, which shows maximum absorbance at 291 nm.

Figure2: UV spectra of levosulpiride expressing maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) at 291nm

- **Preparation of calibration curve:**

From the working standard solution, aliquots of 0.25 mL, 0.5 mL, 0.75 mL, 1 mL, 1.25 mL, and 1.5 mL were taken and diluted to 10 mL using distilled water. This resulted in solutions with concentrations of 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and 120 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. These solutions were then scanned at 291nm using a blank for reference. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting concentration on the X-axis and absorbance on the Y-axis, demonstrating linearity within the 20-120 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration range⁵.

- **Validation:**

Analytical method validation, as outlined in ICH Q2 (R1), is the process of confirming that a specific analytical procedure is suitable for its intended purpose. This ensures that the method consistently provides reliable, accurate, and precise results in pharmaceutical development and manufacturing. The International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) Q2 (R1) guideline establishes the framework for assessing the performance of analytical methods.

- **Linearity:**

According to the ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines, the linearity of an analytical procedure verifies that the test results have a direct relationship with the concentration (amount) of the analyte within the sample. For the linearity study, six solutions of varying concentrations (20, 40, 60, 80, 100, and 120 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were prepared in 50% methanol from a working standard solution of levosulpiride. The absorbance of each solution was measured at 291 nm using UV-visible spectroscopy. A calibration curve was plotted by graphing absorbance against concentration. The percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) and the coefficient of correlation (R^2) were determined using regression analysis to assess the method's linearity⁶.

- **Precision:**

According to ICH guidelines, the precision of an analytical procedure refers to the consistency of results obtained from multiple measurements of the same homogenized sample. To evaluate precision, both repeatability (intra-day precision) and intermediate precision (inter-day precision) were assessed. For repeatability, six replicate measurements of an 80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration ($n=6$) were performed on the same day, and the percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) of the assay results was calculated. Similarly, to assess intermediate precision, the same concentration was analysed in six replicates over three consecutive days, and the %RSD was determined.

- **Accuracy**

The accuracy of the investigation was evaluated using the standard addition method. In this approach, a known amount of the standard was added at three different levels 50%, 100%, and 150%—to the in-house tablet formulation of levosulpiride. The samples were then analysed using the developed method in triplicate. To assess the percentage recovery of levosulpiride, varying amounts of the standard (50%, 100%, and 150%) were spiked into the in-house tablet formulation. Determine the accuracy of the proposed method, recovery studies were carried out by using nine determinations over 3 concentration levels (50%, 100%, and 150%), covering the specified range in replicates. Results are shown in the table.

50% level:

From the above stock solutions, 0.4ml (40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) is taken and transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask and finally make up with diluent.

100% level:

From the above stock solutions, 0.8 ml (8 μ g/ml) is taken and transferred into 10ml volumetric flasks and finally make up with diluents.

150% level:

From the above stock solutions, 1.2 ml (120 μ g/ml) is taken and transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks and finally make up with diluents.

Acceptance criteria:

The % recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0 %.

- **Detection Limit (LOD) and Quantification Limit (LOQ):**

The limit of detection (LOD) refers to the smallest quantity of an analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily measured with precision. On the other hand, the limit of quantification (LOQ) is the lowest concentration of an analyte that can be reliably measured with accuracy and precision. For levosulpiride, LOD and LOQ values were determined following ICH guidelines, using the residual standard deviation of the response and the slope of the calibration curve obtained from the linearity study. The LOD was calculated using the formula $(3.3 \times \sigma) / S$, while the LOQ was determined using $(10 \times \sigma) / S$, where σ represents the standard deviation of the response, and S is the slope of the calibration curve. This ensures that the detection and quantification limits are established based on statistically validated parameters, improving the reliability of the analytical method.

- **Robustness:**

Robustness refers to the ability of an analytical method to produce consistent and reliable results across different laboratories or varying conditions without significant deviations. A robustness test is designed to evaluate this characteristic. To assess the robustness of the proposed method, absorbance measurements were conducted using multiple UV spectrophotometers available in different laboratories⁷.

- **Stability studies:**

A forced degradation study of levosulpiride was performed to evaluate its stability under various stress conditions. The investigation examined the effects of oxidation, temperature, photolysis, and hydrolysis across a broad pH range. Oxidation was induced using a 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) solution, while acidic hydrolysis was conducted with 0.1M hydrochloric acid (HCl) and basic hydrolysis with 0.1M sodium hydroxide (NaOH).

The sample was subjected to thermal stress by heating it to a temperature between 60-70°C for one hour. For photolysis, the sample solution was exposed to UV light.

- **Assay:**

The UV spectroscopic method proposed was applied to determine the concentration of levosulpiride in an in-house tablet formulation. The results from three separate analyses showed that the average percentage of levosulpiride present in the tablets was 98.80%. This method holds potential for routine use in future studies involving levosulpiride analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

- **Linearity**

The calibration curve, representing absorbance versus concentration, exhibited linearity within the concentration range of 20 to 120 μ g/mL, as illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. The relative standard deviation (RSD) was determined to be low at 0.006%, while the correlation coefficient (r^2) was calculated as 0.998 (Table 1). These results confirm that the test measurements were directly proportional to the analyte concentration in the sample

To determine the accuracy of the proposed method, recovery studies were carried out by using nine determinations over 3 concentration levels (50%, 100%, and 150%), covering the specified range in replicates. Results are shown in the table.

50% level:

From the above stock solutions, 0.04ml (4 μ g/ml) is taken and transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask and finally make up with diluent.

100% level:

From the above stock solutions, 0.08 ml (8 μ g/ml) is taken and transferred into 10ml volumetric flasks and finally make up with diluents.

150% level:

From the above stock solutions, 0.12 ml (12 μ g/ml) is taken and transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks and finally make up with diluents.

Acceptance criteria: The % recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0 %.

Figure3: Calibration curve of Levosulpiride

Table 1: Results of Linearity

Concentration (mcg/ml)	Absorbance
20	0.153
40	0.279
60	0.382
80	0.518
100	0.644
120	0.783

Figure4: overlay spectrum of Levosulpiride at 291nm

- **Precision**

The relative standard deviation (RSD) values for intra-day and inter-day precision tests are presented in Tables 3. For an analytical method to be considered precise, the %RSD of assay results from six replicates should not exceed 2%. In the intra-day precision test, the RSD values for six replicates measured at three different time points within the same day were 0.364383 %, similarly, for the inter-day precision test conducted over three consecutive days, the RSD values were 0.452824%. The low %RSD values confirm the precision of the method.

Table2: Results of precision

S.N0	Intraday	Interday
1	0.522	0.509
2	0.519	0.506
3	0.518	0.509
4	0.519	0.513
5	0.517	0.511
6	0.522	0.512
Mean	0.5195	0.51
Std. Dev	0.001893	0.002309
% RSD	0.364383	0.452824

- **Accuracy**

The accuracy of the study was evaluated using the standard addition method by testing three different concentrations of levosulpiride: 40, 80, and 120 µg/ml. The percentage recovery ranged between 98% and 100%, with a relative standard deviation (% RSD) of --%.

Table3: % of accuracy

S. No	Conc. Level	Absorbance (n=3)	Amount added (mcg/ml)	Amount found (mcg/ml)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
1	50%	0.257	39.82	39.69	99.66	100.70
2		0.259		40	100.44	
3		0.263		40.61	101.99	
4	100%	0.524	80.05	80.92	101.09	101.02
5		0.521		80.46	100.51	
6		0.526		81.23	101.48	
7	150%	0.777	120.07	120	99.93	99.42
8		0.773		119.38	99.42	
9		0.769		118.76	98.90	

- **LOD&LOQ**

The Limit of Detection (LOD) refers to the lowest concentration of an analyte that can be reliably detected with acceptable precision and accuracy under the specified conditions of the method. The LOD may vary depending on the analytical technique used and the characteristics of the sample. For levosulpiride, the LOD

was determined to be 0.97 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, while the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) was found to be 2.95 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. These values were calculated using equations derived from the calibration curve and have been reported accordingly.

Table4: Results of LOD & LOQ

S.No	Parameter	Slope	Std. Dev	Observation (mcg/ml)
1	LOD	0.0064	0.00189	0.97
2	LOQ			2.95

- Robustness**

The method's robustness was evaluated by varying the solvent ratios as ± 5 (45% and 55%) and using different wavelengths ± 3 (288 nm and 294 nm) while maintaining a constant concentration of 80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The results remained consistent and reproducible, confirming the method's validation.

Table5: Results of Robustness

S. No	Parameter	Condition	Absorbance (Mean \pm SD)	% RSD
1	Wavelength (± 3 nm)	288	0.502 \pm 0.0024	0.49
2		291	0.518 \pm 0.00082	0.15
3		294	0.498 \pm 0.00124	0.25
4	Solvent Proportion ($\pm 5\%$)	45	0.495 \pm 0.00094	0.19
5		50	0.508 \pm 0.00205	0.40
6		55	0.514 \pm 0.00094	0.18

- Stability studies**

To develop a stability-indicating method, the UV spectra of levosulpiride were examined under various stress conditions using a UV/Vis spectrophotometer. The percentage degradation of the drug under each condition is shown in Figure 6. Based on the results, it can be concluded that levosulpiride undergoes degradation within acceptable limits under all tested conditions.

Table6: Results of stability studies

S. No	Stress condition	Absorbance	% Assay	% Degradation
1	0.1 M HCl	0.471	108.07	8.07
2	0.1 M NaOH	0.486	104.73	4.73
3	3.0 % v/v Peroxide	0.487	104.52	4.52
4	Thermal	0.509	100.2	0.2
5	Photolytic	0.488	104.3	4.3

CONCLUSION

A reliable, precise, and cost-effective UV spectroscopic method has been successfully developed for the estimation of levosulpiride in both bulk and in-house tablet formulations. This method is simple, rapid, and robust, making it suitable for routine analysis. The precision of the method is confirmed by a relative standard deviation (RSD) of less than 2%, indicating high reproducibility. Accuracy studies show a recovery rate between 98-99%, demonstrating excellent accuracy and specificity. Additionally, the high percentage of drug recovery confirms that excipients in the tablet formulation do not interfere with the analysis, proving the method's specificity and effectiveness. Given its reliability, the developed UV spectroscopic method is well-suited for the routine quality control analysis of levosulpiride in pharmaceutical formulations.

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